

Green Technologies: Power from Beneath the Earth – The Potential Role of Geothermal in Agri-Food Sector

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Abstract

The share of agriculture accounted for 19.9% in 2020-2021 in the global GDP and it remains one of the most significant sectors of global-economy as it links various social, economic and environmental aspects with global contemporary issues. Being one of the largest sectors, it emits around 26% of the world's Greenhouse Gases-(GHGs), however, to meet the ever-elevating needs of food and other plant products in today's world, agriculture, which heavily relies on conventional energy-resources, is directing towards renewable energy resources like geothermal, the boundless energy, extracted from below the Earth's surface. The direct-applications of geothermal-heat in the agri-food industry have provided farmers and producers a new light for enhancing productivity, food-quality, energy-security, cost-efficiency and long-term sustainability by cutting GHGs-emission to around 80% from various agri-food sectorial activities. Global geothermal capacity for direct use accounts for almost 107,727 MWt with the growing-rate of 8.7% per annum. Exploited in multiple ways, low to moderate (20-140°C) geothermal-heat is used in soil-heating, cultivation, industrial processing, food-drying, irrigation in more than 82 countries, internationally, among which greenhouse-heating is largely developing in the nations of extreme weathers for crop, vegetables, fruit and floral cultivation and fish-farming on a commercial-scale. Iceland started utilizing geothermal in the 20th-century and has developed its agro-economy since then by producing food in greenhouses, using geothermal, even cultivating non-native species and novel crop-varieties. However, large-scale geothermal deployment faces issues, such as capital-risk, technical-barriers, policy regulations and issues related to seismicity in geographically-sensitive areas, as it requires drilling and huge capital. Yet, the utilization of geothermal has expanded worldwide, as the benefits of geothermal outweigh the cons of its utilization.

Keywords: Geothermal Energy, Agri-food Sector, Industrial-Processes, Geothermal-Heat, productivity, Food-Security, sustainability

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1.0 Introduction

1.1 The Food-Energy Nexus & Geothermal Energy: A Brief Background

“The right question is usually more important than the right answer”, quoted Plato.

The dynamics of global-issues that determine human existence in the contemporary world, involve the triad challenges of overpopulation, environmental-degradation and related resource & food-insecurities, incorporating the paradox of surplus of resources for some while resource-deficiency for others. The global-population is constantly soaring, currently accounting for ~7.9 billion, which, as per the new medium-variant projections, will be upshifted to 9.1 billion in 2050 (Prosekov and Ivanova, 2018; Singh et al., 2019). Moreover, ~70% of the global-population is projected to be urbanized by 2050, causing a mass-transition from grower to consumer class, which will impend enormous pressure on the global agricultural-capacity to meet the world’s food-demand without compromising the physical-state of natural-resources (Robertson and Swinton, 2005). The global food-demand projections reflect a massive surge from 35% to 56% for 2010 & 2050, respectively (Van Dijk et al., 2021). The international productivity per capita of the sectors of agriculture, fisheries & forestry has also increased in the last few decades with the increased GDP-share of 3.4% in 2000 to 4.3% in 2020 (World Bank Group, 2022), however, being the world’s largest and energy-intensive industry, agri-food industry (including production, harvest, & supply-chain i.e., storage, processing, packaging, transportation, retail and marketing) (Fig.1) consumes 30% of global-electricity and is responsible for ~26% of the world’s GHGs-emissions (FAO, 2021).

Figure 1. A Chart Showing GHGs-Emissions by Activities or Divisions of the Agri-food Industry (Redrawn After Roser and Ritchie, 2022) (See Appendix 1.)

The food-energy nexus is socially, environmentally & economically significant as over 2.5 billion people primarily rely on agri-food industry for their livelihoods worldwide, however, the modern food-energy system extensively relies on fossil-fuel based conventional resources, generating high environmental-footprint while influencing the overall food- costs (Bardi et al., 2013), thereby undermining the food-quality & food-security (IRENA, 2021). ~8.9% of the global-population is facing moderate to severe food-insecurity (Roser and Ritchie, 2022), thus, the food-energy nexus has been aligned with the 2030 United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) to gradually decouple the dependency on non-renewables, reduce GHGs-emissions, promote sustainable-agriculture & establish food-security (See appendix.2). The diversification of energy-resources, introduction of prime unconventional and decertified-renewables into the agri-food sector can offer multiple benefits, ranging from increased productivity, revenues and energy-security to decreased food-costs, food-insecurity and carbon-emissions (IRENA, 2016).

One of the consistent and potential renewable alternatives is geothermal energy, the inexhaustible heat-energy, stored in the magma and contained in the interior of Earth, where the temperatures are extreme. Geothermal has been one of the reliable electricity-generating resources since 1904, after which its use expanded rapidly across the globe, however, the archaeological evidences feature its use from the pre-industrial age, in 11,000 BC Japan for hot spring-bathing (Fridleifsson, 2001; Barbier, 2002). Independent of the weather-conditions, geothermal has a high capacity-factor, which varies with the characteristics of chemical-reactions under the surface, the degree of crystallization of dissolved-matters & location of each geothermal-reservoir. The direct primary-utilization of geothermal-heat in various applications has been identified in over 83 countries with the global geothermal-capacity of 13,931 MW, 2019 (IRENA, 2021). To accelerate the deployment and foster the visibility of geothermal, bring new investments in the field, enhance dialogue among public and private-actors, generating a strong multi-stakeholder web in the global energy-market, the Global Geothermal Alliance-GGA was launched at COP21, 2015, with 80-member nations & various partner-institutions, bringing new light to expand the scope of geothermal-applications into one of the world's important economic-sectors, the agri-food sector (IRENA, 2019).

Although the exceptionally-potential Geothermal systems can only be established in the regions, closer to plate-boundaries, ~10,000 meters of land-surface consist ~50,000 times more energy than the fossil-fuel resources, globally (Shere, 2013). Agricultural-productivity relies on the availability of land, water, energy- resources. The challenge to meet the global food-

requirements has three-dimensions: ‘high-productivity’, ‘processing and bulk-storage of produced-food’ & ‘food-waste’, thus, exploiting boundless geothermal-energy for heating and cooling in agri-business such as, food-cultivation in barns, greenhouses, industrial-processing, drying, preservation, storage, aquaculture, animal-husbandry, pasteurization, soil warming, underground mushroom-cultivation & irrigation-processes is a way to remarkably increase the food-productivity, quality and decrease cost-volatility, in international-markets (FAO, 2015; Lund, 1986).

2.0 Applications of Geothermal in the Agri-Food Sector

Widely distributed and suitable for direct-utilization, low to moderate geothermal-resources (i.e., ranges from 20°C-140°C) make a compelling economic-case in agri-food sector as the costs of geothermal-technologies have become highly competitive and are estimated to constantly decrease by 2050, providing nations with the customized support to reduce their fossil-fuel dependency, energy-insecurity, food-waste and increase local-employability in the sector while improving public-health. Geothermal-heat has emerged out as a highly efficient-technique to cultivate exotic, non-native species (NNS), worldwide. Additionally, it helps shorten the industrial-processes of drying, distilling while maintaining the original nutrients of the food. The cascaded-utilization of geothermally-heated water enables the reuse of same fluid in different processes at various thermal-levels, reducing primary energy-consumption. Five most promising-applications of geothermal in the form of direct-heat, steam, cascading-water has been identified for the agri-food industry (Popovski, 20019).

Figure 2. A Chart Showing Five Major Direct Applications of in Geothermal in Agri-Food Sector Including, Cultivation, Pre-Harvest, Post-Harvest & Industrial Processes (Redrawn After FAO, 2021).

2.1 Greenhouse-Heating (25°C-100°C)

To cultivate crops, such as fruits, vegetables, floral and exotic species, all year round, geothermal-heat is utilized on a commercial-scale in the greenhouses, worldwide, which provides energy-efficiency with relatively low maintenance and system installation-costs. To achieve constant temperature, relative-humidity in the regions of extreme weather-conditions, various geothermal heating systems are utilized, including the circular-system of hot water-pipes on or beneath the ground to heat the greenhouse-floor, hot water-finned units running along the walls or panels of the potted-benches for the uniform-distribution of heat and various combined-methods. Greenhouses are built with glass, fibreglass or tough-plastics with metal-frameworks, however, the most common and single-layered glass-greenhouses with high illumination-quality, provide low insulation and thus, low energy-efficiency (Rafferty, 1996), which can cause growth-inhibition through shearing, chilling or burning effect in crops, reducing the overall productivity. The heat-loss in fibreglass-greenhouses is similar to the glass-greenhouses, hence, geothermal heating-systems can be a feasible-solution, ensuring energy-conservation, decreasing infiltration and heat-loss. Moreover, it is an efficient alternative of the insulated side-walls & energy-curtains to prevent heat-loss, reducing the size of the heating-module required (Lund, 1996; Bakos et al., 1999).

Around 35 nations practice geothermal-led greenhouse cultivation, globally, which cuts fuel and operating-costs to around 80% and 7%, respectively, as compared to the traditional-resources. It also provides better crop-growing conditions, cleaner-air, hygiene and maintains the consistency of yields and workforce. The cultivation of Californian sweet-pepper & tomatoes in Turkey has become popular in the last one decade. Geothermal-led greenhouse area-cover in Turkey accounts for more than 210.44 ha with the heat-capacity of ~207.44 MWt (FAO, 2015). Kenyan floristry has benefitted hugely through the practice and achieved high export-value, which grew from ~18 to ~110.00 Billion Kenyan-Shilling from 2000 to 2020. Kenya is among the world's largest fresh cut-flowers cultivators, exporters, exporting ~400 million stems of rose per annum (Ngethe and Jalilnasrabady, 2015).

Figure 3. Tomato-Cultivation at Aytekin Polyclima Greenhouse, Turkey, Using Geothermal-Heat (Hortidaily, 2020)

Figure 4. The Harvests of ‘the Queen of Africa Roses’ in a Geothermal-Led Greenhouse, Oserian, Africa by Nichole Sobeck (National Geographic, 2018)

2.2 Soil-Heating (20°C-40°C)

Soil-heating in open or enclosed cultivation-zones can be done by geothermal-heating systems to achieve constant-temperatures, extend growing-seasons and increase the yield. A circular grid of high-temperature resistant and thick-walled (4-5mm) polypropylene corrugated-pipes, spaced at 1.5-2 meters of intervals, 60-85 cm below the surface, contain the high temperature (60°C) inlet-water and warms the soil. The used-water is directed into the pipes at low-temperature (23-25°C), where the flow-rate is maintained throughout the process to keep the soil-temperature to 25-30°C. This technique is majorly utilized to cultivate Brassicaceae and Apiaceae-members in the greenhouses (Kumoro and Kristanto, 2003). In other cases, the smooth or PVC-tubes are laid in parallel-fashion, directly on the greenhouse-surface. These circular-systems act as radiators to circulate heat throughout the cross-section of the land (Bošnjakoviü et al., 2013) for efficient thermal-conductivity.

Figure 5. A Simplified Line-Diagram, Showing a Circular Soil-Heating system, Containing the Inlet (Grey-Arrows) & Outlet Water (Blue-Arrows) Pipes (Van Nguyen et al., 2015).

2.3 Aquaculture (20°C-40°C)

Almost 3.1 billion people rely directly on fish-food for 20% of their daily protein-intake, however, more than 50% of the natural-stocks are fully to partially exploited by overfishing, hence, efficient aquaculture-practices to raise fish and aquatic-flora are crucial (FAO, 2020). Geothermally-heated water is used in either obtaining suitable temperatures by directly mixing it with the fresh-water or to heat the fresh-water in the heat-exchangers for fish-rearing on a commercial-scale. In colder-climates, this direct-application of geothermal has become very common as the heat preserves the natural fish-stocks against harsh weather-conditions and

increase breeding. Molluscs, Salmon, tilapia, prawns, carp, crabs, lobsters, catfish, shrimps, oysters, mussels and many other species are raised worldwide, especially in Iceland, France, U.S.A., Israel & China through geothermal, which brings cost and resource-efficiency to fishery-industries and global-markets (Boyd and Lund, 2006). More than 20 countries have incorporated geothermal-heating in aquaculture for pond, tank or raceway-heating. Geothermally-heated water is mixed with cold-water in the heat-exchanger to achieve the suitable temperature-(20-25°C) before pumping it into the fish-tank. This is effective at hatchery-phase, to initiate fish-cultivation (Fig.6) (Jha and Tripathy, 2017).

Figure 6. A Diagram, Showing the Geothermal-Heat Integration in Aquaculture for Fish-Farming (Van Nguyen et al., 2015)

Despite the water-insecurity and climatic-constrains, Israel has developed efficient aquaculture and majorly produces tilapia, salmon, grey-mullet, grass and silver-carp, extensively, using this practice, wherein tilapia and carp-species collectively account for ~75% of its total inland-aquaculture production. Since 2011, Israel has developed more than 45 geothermal-powered fish-rearing plants (Hulata & Simon, 2011). However, aquaculture also includes aquatic-plant cultivation. The cultivation of blue-green algae like Spirulina, which grows in high-illumination, alkalinity & water-nutrients, has become popular as it has high edible, medicinal

and commercial values, where geothermal is utilized to heat water, derive CO₂ and prepare media. Geothermally-heated water (50-51°C) consists ~4% of pure CO₂/cubic metre of water, which is collected separately to enhance the photosynthesis-process and optimize productivity (Van Nguyen et al., 2015).

2.4 Crop/Food Drying (~60°C-up to 140°C)

Drying agricultural-products can reduce food-waste, enable the availability of nutritious and non-native food, all year round, especially in the regions, vulnerable to droughts, which can significantly reduce energy, oil and spice-usage in the processes (Ogala, 2013). Dried food-products contain <20% of moisture after dehydration, making it suitable for long-term preservation while reducing the costs of storage, packaging and transport at an industrial-scale. However, in developed-nations, drying-processes consume 15-17% of the total industrial-energy with 30-50% of thermal-efficiency, thus, low-enthalpy geothermal-heat can be efficient to remove water-content from the food, while reducing energy-consumption (Chou and Chua, 2001). This is exploited directly through geothermal-reservoirs, steam, hot-water or waste-water. Geothermal driers contain copper or steel-made heat-exchangers, provided with aluminium-fins to heighten the heat transfer-surface. Geothermally-heat or water is directed into these pipes, wherein heat-exchangers blow air through propeller-fans. The air gets high-temperature by hot-water before blowing into the drying-chamber for drying (Fig.7). A range of fruits, vegetables, cereals, beans and other crop-materials can be dried through geothermal-drying; Other direct-techniques involve, fluidized-bed, tunnel or continuous belt-drying, where vegetables and fruits require 75-95°C for complete drying (Sircar et al., 2021).

Figure 7. A Line Diagram of the Design Apparatus of a Geothermal Standalone Drier: The air-blower is usually placed behind the heat-exchanger, blowing air on the heat-exchangers to yield heat from the geothermal-steam or hot-water before entering into the drying-chambers, constructed with stainless-steel treys. Then after the utilized fluid and drying-gas are removed from the system through the outlets pipes (Sumotarto, 2007).

Figure 8. Tunnel-Drying of Tomatoes in Nea Kessani, Xanthi, Greece by Nikos Andritsos: Tomatoes, after washing, are sliced and placed on to the drier-trays of 1 to 2 m wide and tall and rectangular tunnel-driers and dried at 59-60°C for 45-50 minutes with 7 kg of row-tomatoes volume in each batch. After drying, the slices are treated with olive-oil or black-salt to preserve it and packaged for transportation (Van Nguyen et al., 2015).

Figure 9. A 4.0 m Long, 1.35 to 1.40 m Wide Fruit Drier Integrated with Geothermal-Heating, Los Azufres, Mexico: Constructed with concrete and timber roof, this drier can contain 30-

40 treys with the capacity of 1tonnes of fruit-drying/cycle at 60°C; The air is blown through the geothermal steam or hot water, which then after getting the high-temperature passes through the drying-area to remove moisture content from the fruits (Van Nguyen et al., 2015).

2.5 Milk-Pasteurization (70°C-up to 100°C)

Globally, ~600 million tonnes of milk is produced, annually, out of which 128 million tonnes of milk is either wasted or lost (FAO, 2018). Milk is a balanced food, containing fats, carbohydrates and a few vitamins but it deteriorates rapidly as an outcome of the enzymic-activities, temperature-fluctuations and microbial-growth, after collection, thus, processing milk at high-temperatures through pasteurization or Ultra-High Temperature Pasteurization-(UHT) is crucial for its long-term preservation. Geothermal-steam is used in both the processes. Freshly Collected milk (low-temperatures), is pre-heated at 71°C in the heat-exchanger plate-A, after which it is directed to the geothermal plate-B for pasteurization at 78°C for 20-seconds. This milk is then directed to the homogenizer and again back through the heat exchanger plate-A, where it is cooled down to 10-12°C. This milk is chilled at 3°C, afterwards, in the plate heat exchanger-C before the packaging procedures as shown in the (Fig.10). Here, the flow of milk and inlet hot-water (87-88°C) run on either side of the heat exchanger-plates in opposite directions and both the fluids are separated by the gasket plates to avoid mixing (Perko, 2011).

The Mokai geothermal-plant supplies steam to dairy-businesses nearby, to process 250 million litres of milk and other dairy-products, annually, in New Zealand. These dairies export products to 25 nations in the pacific (Van Nguyen et al., 2015).

Figure 10. The Procedure the pasteurization of Milk through Geothermal Steam (Van Nguyen et al., 2015)

2.6 Industrial-Processes

Table 1(continued). A Table Showing the List of Industrial Processes, Crucial in Agri-Food Industry (Van Nguyen et al., 2015; IRENA, 2019)

Process	Description
Evaporation, Distillation (~80°C-120°C)	<p>-The processes of employing fluids to separating mixtures; Mainly utilized in industrial-food processing, like sugar manufacturing, flavour distillation and to increase the concentration of food-materials. The processes can be carried out in batches or a continued-cycle with different amount of heat energy.</p> <p>-Geothermal liquids and steam can be efficiently used in both the processes.</p> <p>-In the evaporator, geothermal-fluid is directed towards the heat-exchangers, discharging heat to dilute concentrated-liquids. The raw-material is passed through the heat-exchanger in the tube, which then circulates to the main body, after getting higher temperature. The boiling-raw material or liquid starts vaporization and the vapour is collected in separate chamber, while the concentrated liquid can be recirculated for the next-cycle.</p>

Bleaching (77°C- 105°C)	<p>-Peeling is one of the important pre-industrial processing steps in the food-processing. For the long-term preservation, some fruits and vegetables are peeled before processing, where they are introduced to the hot-water tanks, which removes the outer layer or skin of the fruits, vegetables and soften them before industrial or mechanical processing.</p> <p>-Before dehydration of the food-products, the raw materials are bleached to avoid enzymic-activities and microbial-growth, where the process shrinks the plant-cells by removing gases. These food-materials are then warmed rapidly at constant temperature for predetermined time-durations and cooled rapidly for the next level processing. Geothermal-fluids provide monitored heat through heat-exchangers and thus are ideal and effective.</p>
Sterilization (>150°C)	<p>-Sterilizing meat or meat-based food products before canning, packaging is extremely important to avoid deterioration, microbial growth and foul-odours. To avoid Clostridium botulinum, food is sterilized at 120-121°C for 3-4 minutes, where geothermal-steam is extremely useful at a commercial-scale. Geothermally heated water (110-120°C) is also utilized to sterilize packaging-bottles and cans in the industries.</p>
Refrigeration (>120°C)	<p>-Geothermal is extensively used for refrigeration through absorption-techniques, which incorporates ammonia/water-cycles (below 0°C). However, the use of geothermal in refrigeration is quite limited to the date at industrial-level.</p>

2.7 Irrigation-Processes (40-80°C)

Geothermally-heated water and steam, after its utilization in various processes, are collected into a pond, where it is cooled down to normal-temperature for irrigation purposes. These ponds vary in size but are usually built, close to the greenhouses. Cultivators utilize various supply-systems to direct it to the greenhouse, however, the chemical-composition of the geothermal-water is analysed before irrigation. Direct pumping of collected water through Surface irrigation perforated-pipes are among the most common methods. The Groundwater Geothermal Heat Pumps-(GWHP) reuses ground-water, used during the heat-extraction and redirect it up-gradient during the winters and during summers, it is used for irrigation (Alberti et al., 2018).

2.8 Cascaded Use

Energy from geothermal-resources can be utilized through integrating various technologies in a sequential-manner in the cascade-systems to heighten the use of low to moderate-geothermal in a rational and sustainable-way. These systems align with polygeneration-systems, making the case for integrated energy-systems. Cascade-utilization enables multiple uses of geothermal at different temperatures from power-generation to various direct-uses, where the heat from geothermal-fluid is extracted subsequently with the progressive decline in the temperature. Kenya is developing novel cascade-systems to fulfil the requirement of electricity and thermal energy carry out food-drying processes, incubation (poultry), apiculture and water-purification though using available geothermal (Rubio-Maya et al., 2015).

Figure 11. A Cascade-System, Integrating Geothermal Energy: A high-temperature geothermal-fluid is directed from the geothermal power-plant after electricity-generation to the industries, where it is utilized for food-processing, distilling, drying and freezing from where the geothermal-fluid with low to moderate temperature is utilized for heating purposes in houses and greenhouses in the areas of non-favourable weather-conditions for plant and mushroom cultivation; At last the same, yet, low-temperature geothermal-fluid is utilized in aquaculture practices for hatchery in fish-rearing and algae-cultivation; This system represents a single-loop process with various tasks on subsequent-stages with various temperatures and heat-requirements (Van Nguyen et al., 2015; Rubio-Maya et al., 2015).

3.0 Iceland: The Successful Case of Geothermal

Located on the mid-Atlantic ridge, between the Eurasian and North American plate, Iceland is a home to potential geothermal-reservoirs, housing ~30 active-volcanoes. Iceland produces from geothermal ~6010 GWh of electricity, accounting for 25% of nation’s overall electricity-generation. Iceland’s economy has grown significantly after the mid-1950s due to the geothermal-deployment (IRENA, 2019). Iceland’s use of renewables per capita is highest in the world (18% hydropower, 68% geothermal).

Figure 12. The Map of Iceland, Showing Volcanic-Regions and Major Geothermal-Zones (Ragnarsson, 2015)

Figure 13. A Pie-Chart Showing the Division of Geothermal Utilization by Sector in Iceland, 2020 (Redrawn After Renewable Energy Cluster | Iceland: The Land of Renewable Resources, 2020)

Moreover, the direct-use of geothermal in fisheries, agriculture, horti and olericulture have become very common, which has significantly improved the food-security while boosting the national-economy through improved GDP-rates. Iceland has a total geothermal-installed capacity of 755MW.

Figure 14. A Graph Showing the Improved Levels of Food-Security in Iceland, 2015-2019 (Redrawn After Renewable Energy Cluster | Iceland: The Land of Renewable Resources, 2020)

Floor-heating in greenhouses through underground or overhead pipes as well as the steel-pipes, running along the walls, carrying geothermal-fluid are very common warming-techniques for plant-cultivation in the shearing-weather of Iceland. Root-vegetable farming is also common in the naturally-hot southern-regions. Along with soil-heating, volcanic-scoria, ash, rhyolite growing-medias are used to increase the yield. Over the last few decades, Iceland has increased the production of tomatoes, Brassicaceae-members, carrots, strawberries, cucumber, mushroom and sweet-peppers, due to the greenhouses-farming with controlled illumination, artificial-lighting, humidity and heat-levels. These factors extend the photoperiodic growing-seasons of the plants, yielding quality-food in good quantities. The greenhouse-cover in Iceland accounts for >250,000 sq. metres, which produces 55% and 45% of the food-plants and flowers, respectively along with ~75%-90% of the domestic-food, consumed in the nation (Ragnarsson, 2015). Iceland started using geothermal for greenhouse-heating in 1924, after which Iceland’s economic-growth and GDP have increased constantly. Some greenhouse-cultivators have gained success to develop new varieties of fruits and vegetables. Greenhouses in Fridheimar have introduced Icelandic-communities to plum-tomatoes, cocktail- tomatoes and Piccolo-tomatoes. Besides that, they produce 370 tonnes of tomatoes, annually, which

accounts for 15% of Iceland’s tomato-market. The greenhouse tourism and dining have become successful, supporting the greenhouse owners with some additional finances (Harper, 2018).

The seafood-industry of Iceland is using the cost-efficient geothermal fluids for fish-farming and indoor-drying and exported 17,462,400kg of fish of ~\$119,023.02K. Indoor fish-drying in Iceland has been practiced for last 37-years, which has made it one of the Europe’s largest fish-exporters, producing salted-fish, cod-backbones, cod-heads etc. About 25 companies’ dry aquaculture-products, utilizing geothermal-energy with the annual-capacity of 2000-4000 tonnes (Arason, 2003). There are more than 70 fish-farms in Iceland, which farm under 20-50°C, using geothermal-heat for juvenile-production. Cage-farming started in early 21st-century for char, salmon and mollusc-production, however, most plants use open sea-water, where constant-temperature (20-35°C) is maintained throughout the year. Iceland utilizes ~2230 TJ geothermal-energy, annually in aquaculture, which is growing each year (Ragnarsson, 2015).

Figure 15. A Geothermal-Integrated Rack Tunnel Drier for Fish-Drying: Primary slot-drying at 20-25°C for 1 to 2 days, after which secondary-drying is carried out at 22-26°C to shrink the body-cells and burn moisture-content for long-term preservation (Van Nguyen et al., 2015).

4.0 Challenges & Future Recommendations

Globally, there are three chief constrains in the acceleration of geothermal-energy in the agri-food sector: Technical, Financial & Policy-regulations.

Table 2(continued). A Table Showing Three Major Challenges in the Wider Deployment of Geothermal (FAO, 2015)

Barrier	Description
Technical	Geothermal, being the uncertain and mega-projects, requires a team of engineers, chartered officers, finance manager, policy-experts. This along with the infrastructure to function smoothly, integrating geothermal is often lacking or insufficiently developed in most nations. Governmental budgetary fund allocations of geothermal in most countries tend to be low.
Financial	Geothermal-projects need large upfront investment from drilling, equipment, workforce and operation, which is lacking in most developing-countries. Its uncertainty of success affects the range of the availability of funding and financial support for the deployment, which discourage investors. Additionally, developing a cost-efficient, sustainable and yet beneficial modules for the deployment at industrial-scale is a challenging task.
Policy-regulations	Although the governments are promoting geothermal, legislation is a primary step before developing a geothermal-project. Government policies are important for financial and technical resource mobilization, bringing public or private investment. A strong web of key stakeholders, institutions and co-ordination is still lacking in most nations, which checks the acceleration of geothermal deployment.

Despite the barriers, geothermal-deployment has wide scopes in the nearer future as it is a boundless renewable. From the previous experience of some countries with wider geothermal-applications, it is identified that the public policies are substantially important in the development, which needs to be aligned with national as well as international-contexts. Addressing key financial constraints, such as resource-risk in the initial-stages of geothermal-projects can help increase the overall investment in the field. Governments and global institutions should have a framework of regional, national financial support-schemes, as the technology is capital-intensive (Van Dijk et al., 2021). Some of pre-existing schemes for

convertible grants cover half costs of development, drilling or provide post-development insurances.

Key geological-knowledge of productive-activities, geological-conditions like temperature, soil-composition, pressure to support the deployment and geothermal project-viability studies is necessary for the project-evaluation, planning. Governments along with actor-institutions should encourage research & development-(R&D), technical assistance programmes to acquire high-quality data to establish the technical-surety of geothermal-deployment and attract investors. Multiple integrated projects promote the partnership among various actors and stakeholders to attract industries to settle close to the geothermal-plants. This economic-alignment is necessary to foster the productivity in the close proximity of the plant. In central-Italy, geothermal plants support domestic small to medium-scale enterprise and promote their food-labels, carrying geothermal-energy to represent sustainability in the market. This encourages fuel-shift and needs stakeholders of public, private-sectors along with the community-support (Van Nguyen et al., 2015; IRENA, 2019).

Strong global-cooperation among various actors to facilitate and widen technical, legislative, commercial insights is necessary to enhance dialogue and spread knowledge of the benefits of geothermal, which can also be aligned with sustainable development goals-framework in various economic-sector to achieve global-sustainability. Global Geothermal Alliance is an international platform, providing support to the stakeholders. Moreover, geothermal-projects require drilling, which needs licensing-processes and various permits from governmental-bodies in pre and post-developmental phases, thus, establishing a burden-free transparent common law-system for geothermal-drilling and deployment can improve the bring more investment into the field, besides it can decrease the project-costs, remarkably. Thereby, the national-governments should rethink and reshape the legal-frameworks for deploying renewables like geothermal, as it is abundant and only needs rational-frameworks to achieve long-term energy, resource and cost-efficiency in both the global-north and south (Barbier, 2002).

5.0 Conclusion

The global food and energy-demands along with the global-population are exponentially increasing, hence, to fulfil the requirements of the contemporary-world, it is vital to consider the potential of not only the mainstream clean-energy resources but also the resources like geothermal, a boundless energy-resource from deep below the Earth's surface. The challenges

of rapid urbanization and food-insecurity can only be handled by addressing agricultural-sector. But the current agri-food sector is chiefly structured on the conventional energy-resources, responsible for ~26% of the global GHGs-emissions (FAO, 2021). Chiefly known for district-heating, geothermal has a range of ‘direct application-uses’, especially in the agri-food industry, that are ecologically and economically-feasible, providing the long-term base-load electricity and heating for pre-harvest, syn-cultivation, post-harvest and supply-chain activities of the sector, globally. Global geothermal capacity for direct use accounts for 107,727 MWt, wherein more than 80 nations have started utilizing it into cultivating food-plants, heating soils and greenhouse for farming, aquaculture, milk-pasteurization, industrial-processing like food-drying, sterilization, distillation, irrigation and in the supply-chain. Although, there are feasibility-constrains in the large-scale deployment of geothermal due to its technical-complications, capital-intensity, multi-layered policy-regulations and narrower public-approaches, it can significantly increase the agricultural-productivity in the regions of energy-deficiency and extreme-weathers, while cutting the carbon-emissions and improving the food-quality. Iceland has successfully exploited geothermal-resources for heating and farming though direct-deployment, that has increased the agricultural-productivity and decreased the national food-insecurity from 1.7 to 1.5% in the last decade and making Iceland one of the biggest exporters of dried-fish and cut-glomers in the European-markets (Ragnarsson, 2015). Despite the benefits, geothermal-deployment for direct-applications in agri-food sector still requires thorough attention, wider research and development-programmes, public-awareness, technical understanding and a general approach, implying its need and urgency to achieve a carbon-free agricultural-framework, lower fossil-fuel dependency, and attain sustainability, globally.

Appendix

1. Global GHGs Emission Breakdown by Sectors and Subdivision in the Agri-Food Sector (Roser and Ritchie, 2022)

Global greenhouse gas emissions from food production

Data source: Joseph Poore & Thomas Nemecek (2018). Reducing food's environmental impacts through producers and consumers. Published in Science. OurWorldinData.org - Research and data to make progress against the world's largest problems. Licensed under CC-BY by the author Hannah Ritchie.

2. The List of United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Aligned with Agri-food Industry and Food-Security (United Nations, No Date).

SGDs	Description
2- Zero Hunger	Aiming healthy nutritious food to all, no deaths from hunger or hunger-directed consequences and food-security
3-Good Health & Well Being	Immunization to increase and establish good global public-health & establishment of better health-care systems
7-Affordable & Clean Energy	Establishment of energy security and promotion of renewable green resources to achieve cost-efficiency; clean drinkable water to all.
9-Industry, Innovation & Infrastructure	Establishing better infrastructure for industries and agriculture and making cities climate resilient.
13-Climate Action	Increase climate-change adaptability and resilience, Taking action to defeat climate change

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